

“PROBLEMS IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE”

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Annotation: *In today's rapidly evolving globalization, the demand for young people who are fluent in foreign languages is growing day by day. This has led to an increase in interest in foreign languages among young people and the widespread popularity of learning foreign languages. However, there are cases when young students make a number of mistakes in the process of learning a foreign language, or encounter some problematic situations, and their interest in new languages quickly disappears.*

Key words: *Education, audio materials, German language, vocabulary*

Объявление: В условиях современной стремительно развивающейся глобализации спрос на молодых людей, свободно владеющих иностранными языками, растет день ото дня. Это привело к росту интереса к иностранным языкам среди молодежи и широкой популярности изучения иностранных языков. Однако из-за ряда ошибок, допущенных учащимися при изучении иностранных языков, или из-за каких-то проблемных ситуаций их интерес к новым языкам быстро пропадает.

Ключевые слова: Образование, аудиоматериале, немецкий язык, словарь

The languages widely used in international communication and international affairs are advanced languages, and today the teaching of a foreign language in most countries of the world is not limited to the borders of their own country, but also interacts with other nations and cultures. Means that it is studied more in order to be effectively recognized and taught. Although modern teaching methods have been developed

to teach foreign languages, especially English, as a foreign language, there are specific challenges in mastering it. **Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-5117 of May 19, 2021 "On measures to bring the promotion of foreign language learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level"** was signed. It is time for our country to launch a new system of foreign language teaching, which will be a solid foundation for the future. Since we have set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must be fluent in **at least 2 foreign languages**. Today, teaching in foreign languages is conducted in **25 higher education institutions** in our country. **In 2016, they were only 7. The number of internationally certified graduates has increased 10 times in the last 3 years.** This is one of our achievements, but many people face many difficulties in learning a foreign language. We will discuss this problem in the article.

After the independence of our country, great attention was paid to the study of foreign languages in every region, district and village of the country. The decision was made on It is important that this decision takes a full place in the structure of primary education as a foreign language subject, and further strengthens the interest of students in learning foreign languages.

"Today's decisions in education policy have a broad impact on the country's scientific, economic, political and cultural needs," said Azamat Akbarov, a professor at Busan University of Foreign Languages in South Korea. The system of teaching foreign languages to children at an early age, which has been introduced for many years, is also in line with our country, and **in 2017-2018 it was proposed to adopt some legislation in this area**, including Tashkent State University of World Languages and Oriental Studies. Along with the Samarkand Institute of Foreign Languages, one university in each region has been identified as a base institution for foreign languages, and the head of state stressed the need to create decent conditions for teachers and encourage them according to their qualifications.

At present, pre-school education, school, lyceum and college students and university students, as well as staff working in various fields, are taught a foreign language, in particular, English, and compulsory education is provided. Became part of. Do many people find it difficult to learn a foreign language these days? It's not easy to learn new language skills properly, but I think a comprehensive education system can overcome that.

So, we will use the following methods to solve problems and make learning English meaningful and interesting.

1. Learning from scratch

Some of us find it very difficult to start learning a new language. Almost every language learning journey starts with the alphabet, which can be difficult for some people.

2. Limited learning environment

When we talk about a limited learning environment, we do not mean the availability of furniture in the classrooms or the location of the school. In many cases, students try to speak English only under the supervision of a teacher. There is also a lack of regular English speakers around the students. As a result, it is difficult to learn and communicate in English. Learning materials, especially books and audio materials, are tools to help with the learning process. Students will learn how to pronounce words and sentences if they follow audio and video assignments in the language they are learning.

3. Hesitation in speaking

Lack of regular communication makes it difficult to speak. This leads us to another challenge we face in learning a foreign language. Many students are reluctant to speak to speakers, so they are embarrassed if they make a mistake. This makes it difficult to learn the language. For example, they think a lot about saying a sentence, they know what it is, but they think about whether it is right or not. It hurts because people don't forget the mistakes they made. By making a mistake, students experience what they have done and know the next step to be better at learning.

4. Grammar problems

Grammar is not important in learning a foreign language, but that does not mean it is not important. It is helpful to have one or more grammar books in the learning process. If you don't understand some grammar rules, ask for help as many times as you fully understand. The grammar of every language, of course, has its own difficult parts, so if you don't understand it from the beginning, it's not the end of the world. Just be patient and exercise a lot. Problems such as adherence to grammar rules and language barriers can stifle students' interest in language acquisition and lead to a lack of seriousness. In fact, I find the idea that sentences do not have to be grammatically correct to make communication understandable to be both partially correct and partially incorrect. This is because grammatical fluency can be compromised if grammatical rules are constantly changed.

5. Not taking it seriously

It should be noted that students often do not take language learning seriously. In addition, in schools, high schools, colleges, and non-philological universities, students treat foreign languages as a secondary subject. Unfortunately, in most cases, students learn the language during the lessons. After class or independent study, they do not practice pronunciation, essay writing, or learning new words on their own. One of the biggest shortcomings is that when mistakes are corrected, the idea that **"this is not my language"** often takes root in the minds of students. This has a negative effect on learning a foreign language.

6. Thinking in another language

Many people think in their native language when they start learning a new language. They tend to translate words into their native language, which of course takes time. However, with this, they become more and more confused. Each language speaks for itself, so don't think that your mother tongue is very similar to the language you are learning. We do not recommend direct translation.

7. Try ways to form a dictionary

Dictionary is one of the most important aspects of this language. Some scholars claim that more vocabulary helps students achieve more success in the target language. **According to Al-Qahtani (2015)**, low vocabulary knowledge can cause serious problems for students. The dictionary plays an important role in the teaching and learning of a second language, as lexical knowledge is the basis for communicating with non-native English speakers.

As Rechard and Renandya (2002) pointed out a few years ago, people's language depends on the dictionary used or derived. Lack of vocabulary deprives students of motivation to use.

As Gaubert (1997) points out, students go through four stages in learning a dictionary:

I. Discrimination

II. Understand the meaning

III. Remember the meaning

IV. Consolidation and expansion phase

The first is discrimination, where students speak and listen because by distinguishing sounds, students pronounce words correctly and understand them when they see or hear them in context. They understand the meaning of words by linking them to their meanings. The third is the ability to remember meanings. Finally, the consolidation and expansion phase

requires students to explore the new vocabulary and its integration. You have seen that vocabulary is one of the most important aspects of language. **According to Oxford (1990)**, there are no rules in the study of vocabulary, because we have strict rules in the study of grammar. Everyone chooses a convenient dictionary method. I also have a convenient dictionary rejuvenation style for myself. For example, when I was studying German, I had five science books, and I devoted one section to each subject, depending on my level and interests, such as food, household items, politics, finance, and music. Then, for a few weeks, I would focus on studying the words related to these five main topics and classifying them separately. When I look up a dictionary, I look at them by topic. Then I make a list of synonyms. Many students complain about this, and *Thomas Edison*, one of his 27 lab technicians, found six lanterns every day for a month on the road to the factory's main building in **Menlo Park, New Jersey**. A cherry tree was growing along the way, but when 27 people were interviewed, it turned out that none of them had noticed it at all. All this is due to the evil of human observation. Young people, in general, need observation for all people. This is the first way to improve memory. Another key factor in strengthening memory is reading aloud. Lincoln used two senses to represent the information needed by the mind. **"When I read aloud, the thought is received by two senses," he said. Firstly, I see what I read, and secondly, I hear it, so I remember it very well."**

In conclusion, in order to avoid mistakes and problems in the process of learning foreign languages, it is necessary to be more responsible than to learn the language, to work on it regularly. Not only sound education but his alertness and dedication too are most required. Only then can you fully master the language you are learning.

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